

Spermidine restores the number of peripheral blood leukocytes and their subsets in rat model of Parkinson's disease

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Introduction:

Parkinson's disease (PD) is characterized by progressive loss of the neurons in the substantia nigra pars compacta (SNpc) and its input to the striatum (CPU). Although the etiology of PD is not fully elucidated, neuroinflammation and peripheral immune cell infiltration are believed to be one of the mechanisms contributing to the PD pathology [1]. Spermidine (SPER), a natural polyamine, possesses anti-oxidant, anti-aging properties and its anti-inflammatory potential still being assessed [2].

Aim:

The aim of this study was to test the potential effects of SPER long term treatment on peripheral blood leukocytes number changes in progressive neurodegeneration in rat model of PD.

Methods:

Male Wistar rats (n=34) received infusion of 6-hydroxydopamine (6-OHDA, 24µg dissolved in 4 µl 0.02% ascorbic acid solution) or *vehiculum* (VEH) into dorsal and ventral CPU in right hemisphere. One day after, rats were treated with 10mg/kg SPER or placebo (PL) oral supplementation for next 30 days. Blood samples were collected from the tail vein before PD model induction (baseline) and 30 days after. The samples were analyzed using ABX Micros 60 Hematology Analyzer. Kruskal-Wallis tests were used to analyze obtained data (SPSS v.21).

Results:

We found that the number of peripheral blood leukocytes, lymphocytes and monocytes decreased in rats with PD model compare with baseline ($p \leq 0,05$; $p \leq 0,05$; $p \leq 0,01$) and VEH ($p \leq 0,05$; $p \leq 0,05$; $p \leq 0,01$). Long-term SPER treatment in rats with PD elevated blood leukocytes, lymphocytes and monocytes number compares to 6-OHDA group ($p \leq 0,05$; $p \leq 0,01$; $p \leq 0,001$).

Conclusion:

Spermidine treatment has beneficial effects on peripheral blood leukocytes number in the progressive rat model of PD.

References:

[1] doi: 10.3389/fneur.2019.00232

[2] doi: 10.1126/science.aan2788

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